

LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE

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Abstract: This study focuses on the importance of the Latin language for medical students in the preparation of a terminologically literate paramedical worker.

Keywords: Latin language, term, terminology, medicine.

Relevance. The discipline "Latin and Medical Terminology" is an integral part of the training of any medical specialty. The assimilation of this discipline in the first year contributes to the preparation of students of secondary vocational education, and ultimately the formation of a terminologically competent average medical worker.

Target. The purpose of this article is to show that the creation of the necessary knowledge base of Latin terms and special concepts is of great importance in various disciplines. This study is based on an analysis of the performance of students of the SamSMU.

Introduction. In the preparation of future specialists in the field of medicine, the study of the Latin language is undoubtedly of great importance. Already in the first year in medical science, students meet special concepts in Latin. Therefore, it is necessary to attach special importance to its study not only as the language of one of the most ancient cultures, but also as a language necessary in the practical activities of a medical specialist.

In the modern world, any more or less educated person must understand the endless variety of terms that are full of advertising posters, booklets and leaflets. This is especially true for medical terms. Time dictates its conditions and in order to understand the numerous terms that exist in medicine, you need to know Latin and Greek, as they are one of the disciplines that are of great importance in the training of specialists in the field of medicine and pharmacy, you have to meet them in everyday life. work - when reading the names of diseases, anatomical and clinical terms, the names of medicinal raw materials, botanical terms adopted in the International Nomenclature for the Names of Chemical Compounds and especially in the formulation.

A modern doctor, even when he speaks Russian on a professional topic, uses more than 60% of the words of Latin and Greek origin. And this is not surprising,

because it is well known that the terminologies of various sciences, including those that have arisen relatively recently, have been replenished and continue to be replenished due to the active involvement, direct or indirect, of the vocabulary and word-formation means of these two classical languages of the ancient world.

All of us at least once bought medications or went to the doctor. Any medicines have the same Latin name, except for the main one. Every medical student knows by heart the name of all organs and bones in Latin. Why is Latin still so important?

The roots of the Latin language go back to the deep past, to a tribe of militant Latins who inhabited in ancient times a small region of the Apennine peninsula "Latium" and founded the city of Rome. The tribe spoke exclusively in Latin. As a result of the wars of conquest, a number of regions joined this region, such as Macedonia and Greece, Syria and Egypt, regions in the north of the Balkan Peninsula, North Africa, Gaul, Britain and a number of other lands of the then known world. The power of ancient Rome grew, the language spread along with it. The Latin language was considered a manifestation of high culture. Throughout the territory of a huge power, Latin was the official, state language. Latin was also the language of jurisprudence, diplomacy, Catholic churches and literature. Over time, the Latin language began to be gradually replaced by the Greek language. A large number of Greek words appeared in Latin. This is where the close interweaving of Greek and Latin comes from. Currently, the study of Latin is of great importance in the training of a mid-level medical specialist, as it helps to consciously assimilate and understand the medical terms of Latin Greek origin, which he will meet and use in their practice.

Since ancient times, physicians have known the following Latin proverb: *In via est in medicina via sine lingua Latina* - The path in medicine is impassable without the Latin language.

This statement is true even today.

The first works on medicine were written by the ancient Greeks and Romans. We still use the terminology proposed by ancient scientists thousands of years ago. And, of course, everyone knows that the great Hippocrates wrote his works in Greek.

Medical terms - anatomical, clinical, pharmaceutical - are mostly words of Latin-Greek origin. Therefore, medical education is impossible without knowledge of the basics of this terminology.

There are a lot of words of Latin origin in Russian. For example, the word student comes from the Latin verb studere (student) - which means to study; praeparare (preparation) - which means to prepare; audire-(audience) - to hear; auscultare (auscultation) to listen; repetere-(tutor) - repeat; signare-(signature)- to signify, etc.

In our time, the meaning of language has not been lost. In the description and classification of diseases, Latin has no equal.

Although Latin is considered dead today, it is still an integral part of the work of every physician. Separate Latin aphorisms and sayings relate to issues of life and death, human health, and the behavior of a medical worker. Some of them are medical deontological (Greek deon, deonios - "due" + logos - "teaching") commandments, for example: Solus aegroti suprema lex medkorum - "The good of the patient is the highest law of doctors"; Primum noli nocere! "First of all, do no harm!" (The first commandment of a medical worker.)

In medicine, as in any other field, there are terms, concepts and designations that fill the language, and they cannot be deleted.

Without knowledge of the Latin language, it is impossible to study such disciplines as anatomy, pharmacology, and clinical disciplines.

Conclusion. Thus, it can be said with sufficient certainty that:

In order to correctly understand and construct medical terms, you need to master the basics of medical terminology in Latin, and they must be laid in the first year through the practical study of the elements of grammar and the principles of word formation;

The student's enthusiasm and his independent work expand the cognitive and educational moment of studying Latin and its interdisciplinary connections with other disciplines of the educational cycle.

The study of Latin helps students in the conscious assimilation and competent use of the professional language of the future specialist.

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